

Machine Learning in Artist Review (Capturing Customers Feedback and Emotions in Large Computing Courses: A Sentiment Analysis Approach)

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Abstract— This paper discusses an aspect-based Sentiment Analysis (SA) approach for reviewing artists. The method looks at the overall sentiment a sentence conveys as well as giving a different sentiment to each individual sentence component. The Vader algorithm is typically recommended by this study to categorize patron attitudes toward the artist. Sentiment analysis is extensively employed in marketing, customer service, clinical medicine, and other sectors to examine comments and survey results, online and social media content, and healthcare materials. When reading customer reviews, it's easy to tell whether the reviewer is happy, upset, or neutral.

Keywords—Sentimental Analysis, artist review, vader

I. INTRODUCTION

Not everyone responds the same way to music. A music may elicit positive emotions in certain listeners but unpleasant emotions in others. The song's words have the power to affect a person's behaviour. Looking back in time, we can see that there have been occasions when songs have been written to compel listeners to dance, sing, march, or engage in combat.

In summary, this study suggests categorizing customer reviews of the art using the Vader algorithm before performing sentiment analysis on the feedback. The findings of this survey should show how customers view any artist. In order to better manage the market and compel more listeners, the artist might use the information obtained to create customer relationship management.

II. METHODOLOGY

Document data collecting via review data crawling is the first stage of the data collection process for this project. The data set is then prepared for processing using preprocessing text. The Vader algorithm is employed in the following feature to analyse the positive, negative, and neutral words. and show the positive general tone of the assessment.

1. II.a. Data Collecting

Paper's formatting and text styling are done using the template. There may be oddities, but all margins, column widths, line spacings, and text fonts must follow the rules. For instance, this template's head margin is proportionately larger than usual. This measurement and others are intentional; they follow guidelines that assume your paper will be a component of the full procedure and not stand alone.

II.a. NLTK (Natural Language Processing Toolkit)

We are utilizing approaches and techniques for natural language processing. In order to analyze sentiment, we are utilizing the NLTK 2.0.4-powered categorization process for text. A user types emoticons, punctuation, and feelings about them.

Our objective is to simply dissect the review in order to determine their opinion about our service. We view reviews as capturing the opinions of individuals and organizations. The core pay attention to factors like the number of positive, negative, and neutral words.

III. DATA CLEANING

The text is so severely unstructured that it needs to be cleaned up and prepared before being evaluated. Data cleaning involves a lot of tasks. In this case, text is the only thing that matters. The text from the review was converted into a data frame by us. The use of URLs, stop words such "the," "a," and "to," extraneous spaces, numerals, and punctuation were also removed, and the encoding was converted from latin1 to ASCII. After the text has been cleaned up and extra symbols have been deleted, the analysis is conducted..

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The Bitext Sentiment Analysis tool assigns sentiment to each topic in a single sentence, in contrast to traditional sentence-based sentiment analysis methods. The internal process is comprised of these steps: A text is first broken down into its component tokens, sentences, phrases, and entities.

V. OVERALL DESIGN

This project involves developing a sentiment analysis that precisely pinpoints users' feelings. It is able to assess a large amount of feedback data. In order to construct this project, the Python modules Vader and Flask were used. Operation-based on natural language, such as sentiment analysis, is possible with the Vader sentiment. The sentiment is divided into three categories using the Vedar algorithm: positive, negative, and neutral. Prerequisites

- **Flask**

Flask is a microweb framework built on Python. It falls under the category of a microframework because it doesn't call for any particular tools or libraries. It is devoid of any parts that a database abstraction layer, form validation, or other parts that are commonly provided by existing third-party libraries.

- **Sklearn**

Scikit-learn is probably the Python machine learning library that is most useful. The sklearn toolkit includes a number of efficient machine learning and statistical modelling methods, including dimensionality reduction, clustering, regression, and classification.

- **Requests**

The built-in GET, POST, PUT, PATCH, and HEAD methods of the Python requests module can be used to send HTTP requests to a specified URI. A HTTP request can either push data to a server or retrieve it from a specified URI. It functions as a client-server request-response protocol.

- **NLTK**

A Python library that can be used for NLP is called NLTK, or Natural Language Toolkit. Unstructured data with human-readable text makes up a large portion of the data that you could be studying.

- **RE**

The functions in this module allow you to determine whether a particular string matches a given regular expression. A regular expression provides a collection of strings that it matches.

- **VaderSentiment**

Specifically adapted to the attitudes conveyed in social media, VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) is a lexicon and rule-based sentiment analysis tool that also performs well on texts from other domains.

MUSICOS REVIEW PANEL

"Sentiment Analysis"

Say Something: ...

Submit

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Sentiment of

'this artist made my day, loved it'
is 80.0% positive !

Score table

SENTIMENT METRIC	SCORE
Positive	0.565
Neutral	0.435
Negative	0.0
Compound	0.8

Using consumer sentiment analysis, sentiment analysis is a technology that supports decision-making. a sentiment analysis tool that enables users to make choices based on what other people think about a product. It supports businesses in understanding what their customers want, takes into account their products, and contributes to the creation of the best plans for satisfying customer wants and providing the

best services. We use natural language processing to analyze the sentiment of review data and classify it as either positive, negative, or neutral. We utilized the Python Flask framework to display sentiment analysis on a web site.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, a method for analyzing consumer reviews of an artist's works of art is presented. Natural language processing is used to perform sentimental analysis in the suggested model. Additionally, the system offers consumers who submit reviews of the service anonymity. Since the users' identities are concealed, they can give honest comments.

With a larger dataset, the system will be more accurate and more efficient. The data set can be expanded and used as a reference for future work.

VI. REFERENCE

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